

Trusting the Deficit: Counseling and Substance Abuse

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The practice of twenty-first century substance abuse counseling is well on its way towards some fundamental changes. The innovative approaches of different models give new dimensions to need based approach in the treatment of alcohol and substance abuse. It is difficult to believe that only a few years ago the “conventional Wisdom” about substance abuse was built more on mythology than on science. The statement seems to be true across the globe. Although professionals dealing with substance abuse are by and large open to new and healthier therapeutic methods, also most evidence-based treatments do not easily find their way into practice. Natural diffusion processes for innovations in substance abuse treatments are relatively informal and have yielded a widely acknowledged gap between science and community practice. This review focuses on methods for effectively disseminating new treatment methods into practice. Counseling and psycho-educational interventions are in themselves relatively effective in helping practitioners gain proficiency in new clinical approaches.¹ Individual performance feedback and coaching improve the acquisition of clinical skills. (Brigham, 2006). Specific incentives for implementation may also be needed to encourage treatment providers, programs, and systems to adopt new approaches. (William R. Miller, 2006)

Many members of the community and helping professionals, joined the general public in believing that success interventions require “aggressive confrontation, a tearing down of defense, coercion and wariness to avoid being deceived or coned”.² The quest for advancement in substance abuse counseling practice is not just an intellectual exercise. It is a path to real improvement in human beings. The use of substance is just an element of it that need to handle with care.

Substance Abuse: Working Definition

The term substance abuse is often described individuals and professional, which is largely driven by their personal notions and learning. Different groups and Models of treatments that are adopted by institutions and societies define addiction based on their philosophies and experiences. Alcohol Anonymous, Narcotics Anonymous and many others like Therapeutic Community model (TC Model) are based on 12 steps program. Religion and spirituality is at the core of it. Whereas Models like Cognitive Behavioral Treatment (CBT) and Rational Emotive Behavioral Therapy (RET) focus more on psychological and cognitive aspect of intervention. A group of terms is in wide use but of varying meaning.

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In DSM-IV, 'psychoactive substance abuse'³ is defined as a 'maladaptive pattern of use indicated by continued use despite knowledge of having a persistent or recurrent social, occupational, psychological or physical problem that is caused or exacerbated by the use [or by] recurrent use in situations in which it is physically hazardous'(WHO). It is a residual category, with dependence taking precedence when applicable. The term 'abuse'⁴ is sometimes used disapprovingly to refer to any use at all, particularly of illicit drugs. Because of its ambiguity, the term is not used in ICD-10 (except in the case of non-dependence-producing substances); harmful use and hazardous use are the equivalent terms in WHO usage, although they usually relate only to effects on health and not to social consequences. In other contexts, abuse has referred to non-medical or unsanctioned patterns of use, irrespective of consequences. Thus the definition published in 1969 by the WHO Expert Committee on Drug Dependence was 'persistent or sporadic excessive drug use inconsistent with or unrelated to acceptable medical practice'.

Counseling: Working Definition

Majority of us who study counseling, are confident that we know what counseling is and when given an opportunity we are ready and eager to tell others what we do. However, when comes to practice definition of counseling need get redesigned depending upon the need and assessment of the setting.⁵ This may be because of the diversity of counseling approaches, its grounding in many theoretical perspectives, and the range of human problems for which counseling can be helpful. This definitional challenge is made all the more difficult because of the myriad of uses and activities for which the term 'counseling' is applied.

Counseling Psychology is an applied area of psychology. It could be the solution oriented conversation between two individuals aimed at identifying problems and seeking solutions.

The British Association for Counseling (BAC), now the BACP, may have been the first professional association to adopt a definition of professional counseling. *Counseling is the skilled and principled use of relationship to facilitate self- knowledge, emotional acceptance and growth and the optimal development of personal resources. The overall aim is to provide an opportunity to work towards living more satisfyingly and resourcefully. Counseling relationships will vary according to need but may be concerned with developmental issues, addressing and resolving specific problems, making decisions, coping with crisis, developing personal insights and knowledge, working through feelings of inner conflict or improving relationships with others.*

Counseling is used to help individuals to deal with variety of problem situations. During counseling, the counselor establishes a warm, supportive, therapeutic relationship with the client using a variety of skills. Based on the strength of this relationship, the counselor helps the client explore problem areas, set goals and assists the client to work through problems in order to establish a more meaningful and productive life style. During addiction

treatment, individual counseling aims at enabling the client to learn how to identify and pursue realistic and satisfying solutions to his problems, particularly those related to his chemical abuse.⁶ In order to make individual counseling effective, the counselor has to understand the client as an individual – the influences which have affected him, his perception of himself and others around him – so that she can help the client realize how those forces have led to unhealthy ways of coping both prior to and after the onset of addiction.. This understanding at the level of feelings rather than at the intellectual level (or the objective level), will enable him to cope with life more satisfactorily. The purpose is to help the client in making decisions about his life and enable him to understand the need to take responsibility for his actions as well as their consequences.⁷

Substance abuse counselors work with people who have problems with drugs, alcohol or other substance dependencies to help them recognize issues and behaviors related to their substance abuse and addiction. Some substance abuse counselors also counsel friends and family members of substance abusers. Counseling for substance abuse can take place one-on-one, in a group or a combination of both techniques. The clinical practicums in a substance abuse counseling certificate or degree program can give students hands-on experience working with patients in counseling situations.

Principles for Substance Abuse Counseling

Though, there are some guiding principles of counseling which in a holistic approach need professional training, the practice with a self-disciplined life style is at the core of it. Unique to its values in the field of addiction, recovering addicts by virtue of their own experience at recovery can work as counselors after adequate training. He should have however maintained atleast 3 years of sobriety during which he has made qualitative changes in his life.⁸ He must also be emotionally stable and should have dealt with his personality defects like impulsiveness, irresponsibility, aggressiveness, selfishness and indiscipline.

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The emergent paradigm for substance abuse counseling represent a fresh approach and new mind set. Although the prospective is broad, it does not lend itself to practical guidelines of implementations. Counselor at the cutting edge of practice tend to adhere to a set of practices.⁹

1. Focus on Evidence Based Practice
2. Use of respectful and positive approach to the client
3. View substance abuse problem on continuum from non-problematic to problematic use rather than an either/or situation.
4. Client collaboration and participation
5. Intervention based on realistic problems and social conditions
6. Use of multicultural prospective.
7. Client's Advocacy to the center of counselor's role

Confidentiality is essential in a therapy relationship as part of building trust.¹⁰ However, confidentiality is not absolute, and there are exceptions. Sometimes, in the public interest, counselors may need to make a referral to an agency or organization (for example GP, police or social services) when there is a serious risk of imminent harm to their clients or to others, for example where a client is seriously mentally ill and needs hospitalization, or in cases of child or elder abuse or addiction partner. These referrals are usually (but not always) made with the client's knowledge and consent. This decision will depend on the particular circumstances of each client. There may be times when a therapist is required by law to break confidentiality, for example, about terrorist activities. It may also be a criminal offence to 'tip off' a client when such a disclosure has to be made.¹¹

The Process of Addiction Counseling

For obvious reasons addiction has been termed a baffling illness. Helping the addict overcome this illness calls for an appropriately planned and skillfully managed counseling process.¹² In addiction treatment, counseling offers personal support and guidance to work towards the goal of abstinence from all mood-changing chemicals, and to achieve qualitative lifestyle changes.

The process revolves primarily around the relationship between the counselor and the client. It is this relationship that leads to growth and change. The counselor works 'with' the client, and a sense of partnership and collaboration prevails. In essence, the counselor functions as an ally or guide who helps the client change himself, rather than as an expert who 'fixes' all the client's problems.

The primary goal is to assist the addict in achieving and maintaining abstinence from addictive chemicals and behaviors. The secondary goal is to help the client recover from the damage addiction has caused in his life. That is, the patient is encouraged to achieve and maintain abstinence and then to develop the necessary psychosocial skills to continue recovery as a lifelong process.

Counseling is a process that starts off by building a relationship characterized by rapport and trust with the client. On the basis of this meaningful relationship, the client

is helped to explore problem areas at the levels of both thought and feeling, and identify goals of therapy. Planning, implementing strategies to overcome problems, evaluation and follow-up are the other aspects of the process that follow. The process of counseling moves through five stages¹³ from initiation of the counseling relationship to its termination.

1. Developing a Therapeutic Relationship with Client
2. Exploring Problem Areas
3. Goal Setting
4. Maintaining Change
5. Termination

The process of counseling in case of substance abuse is a long and extended process. Multiple sitting are needed to make it effective and purposeful. Almost all the model recommends 12 to 18 months of treatment followed by a lifelong "under-recovery" rehabilitation. Both client and "significant others" are important stake holders plays an important role in group, family and individual counseling. The twelve step in most of the Therapeutic model programs of de-addiction starts with the "acceptance". The same is generally practiced in process of counseling.

Motivational Interviewing

Motivational interviewing¹⁴ may be helpful at many stages of treatment. It is particularly helpful early in treatment or for individuals who are experiencing problems but do not recognize the severity of their condition. It may be used during the assessment process to determine the individuals' goals and functional level. It is a collaborative, person-centered form of guiding to elicit and strengthen motivation for change. It is an empathic, supportive counseling style that supports the conditions for change. Practitioners are careful to avoid arguments and confrontation, which tend to increase a person's defensiveness and resistance.

Motivational interviewing is a proven and effective way to:

- Engage individuals with co-occurring disorders
- Develop therapeutic relationships
- Determine individualized goals

Motivational interviewing is used for the treatment of many conditions. Specific strategies have been successfully applied to working with individuals with co-occurring disorders include:

- Assessing the person's perception of the problem
- Exploring the person's understanding of his or her condition

- Examining the person's desire for continued treatment
- Ensuring a person's attendance at initial sessions
- Expanding the person's perceptions for the possibilities of successful change

Research shows that motivational interviewing techniques, including counseling, assessment, multiple sessions, and brief interventions, are associated with greater participation in treatment and positive treatment outcomes.¹⁵

Creating Conditions for Change

Practitioners who use motivational interviewing project acceptance rather than censure, which helps free the person to change.¹⁶ Empowering people is an important part improving motivation for change.

Motivational interviewing helps practitioners connect with an individual's intrinsic motivation to change by exploring and resolving ambivalence. It also regards ambivalence to change as normal, expected behavior.

Motivation for change is created when a person recognizes discrepancies between their behavior and their personal goals. The intent of motivational interviewing is to explore the discrepancies with the goal of reducing ambivalence and identifying the individual's goals and priorities. In other words, motivational interviewing helps the person recognize the difference between where they are and where they hope to be.

Five Principles of Motivational Interviewing

The process of interviewing has been *practical* in focus. The strategies of motivational interviewing are more persuasive than coercive, more supportive than argumentative. The motivational interviewer must proceed with a strong sense of purpose, clear strategies and skills for pursuing that purpose, and a sense of timing to intervene in particular ways at incisive moments.¹⁷

The clinician practices motivational interviewing with five general principles in mind:

1. Express empathy through reflective listening.
2. Develop discrepancy between clients' goals or values and their current behavior.
3. Avoid argument and direct confrontation.
4. Adjust to client resistance rather than opposing it directly.
5. Support self-efficacy and optimism.

Besides the established theory Motivational Interviewing, many of therapeutic models like TC strongly recommend Grounding of the clients, most effective than ever. The reason cited is established on the principle of "acceptance"¹⁸ as a therapeutic value to the treatment. Guilt and Shame are used as tool to treatment following the TFA cycle.

Stages of Changes and the Process of Counseling

Counseling in case of substance abuse is a long and continuous process. The role of the counselor may vary during different phases of the treatment. The stages of change model has been helpful for understanding how to enhance clients' motivation. During the recovery process, individuals typically progress and regress in their movement through the stages. Stages of change have been described in several ways, but one especially helpful concept¹⁹ divides the process of changing into five stages²⁰:

- *Pre-contemplation.* At this stage, the person abusing substances is not even thinking about changing drug or alcohol use, although others may recognize it as a problem. The person abusing substances is unlikely to appear for treatment without coercion. If the person is referred, active resistance to change is probable. Otherwise, a person at this stage might benefit from non-threatening information to raise awareness of a possible problem and possibilities for change. While families in this stage may think, "This has to stop!" they frequently resort to often-used defenses such as protecting, hiding, and excusing the IP. When the IP is in the pre-contemplation stage, the therapist works to establish rapport and offer support for any positive change.
- *Contemplation.* A person in this stage is ambivalent and undecided, vacillating over whether she really has a problem or needs to change. A desire to change exists simultaneously with resistance to change. A person may seek professional advice to get an objective assessment. Motivational strategies are useful at this stage, but aggressive or premature confrontation may provoke strong resistance and defensive behaviors. Many contemplators have indefinite plans to take action in the next 6 months or so. In this stage, families waver between "She can't help it" and "She won't do anything." The level of tension and threat rises. The role of the therapist is to encourage ambivalence. Helping the IP to see both the pros and cons of substance use and change helps her to move toward a decision. Client education is an effective tool for creating ambivalence.
- *Preparation.* In this stage, a person moves to the specific steps to be taken to solve the problem. The person abusing substances has increasing confidence in the decision to change and is ready to take the first steps on the road to the next stage, action. Most people in this stage are planning to take action within the next month and are making final adjustments before they begin to change their behavior. One or more family members in this stage begin to look for a solution. They may seek guidance and treatment options. Here, the therapist's role is to encourage the person to work toward his goal. The goal may be as simple as creating a written record of every drink during the time between sessions.
- *Action.* Specific actions are initiated to bring about change. Action may include overt modification of behavior and surroundings. This stage is the busiest, and it requires the greatest commitment of time and energy. Commitment to change is still unstable, so support and encouragement remain important in preventing dropout and regression.

in readiness to change. At this point the forces for change in a family reach critical proportions. Ultimatums and professional interventions are often necessary. The role of the therapist is to encourage the person and continue providing client education to reinforce the decision to stop substance abuse.

- **Maintenance.** Day-to-day maintenance sustains the changes prior actions have accomplished, and steps are taken to prevent relapse. This stage requires a set of skills different from those that were needed to initiate change. Alternative coping and problem solving strategies must be learned. Problem behaviors need to be replaced with new, healthy behaviors. Emotional triggers of relapse have to be identified and planned for. Gains have been consolidated, but this stage is by no means static or invulnerable. It lasts as briefly as 6 months or as long as a lifetime. In maintenance the family adjusts to life without the involvement of substances.²¹ During this stage it is important to maintain contact with the family to review changes and potential obstacles to change. Reminding family members that it is a strength, not a weakness, to use support to maintain changes can help them relate to what should be the therapist's enthusiasm for recovery of not only the IP, but for the entire family. The therapist's goal is relapse prevention; to teach the IP and family about relapse, how to prepare for difficult times and places, and to never give up.

Termination (entered from the maintenance stage) is the exit—the final goal for all who seek freedom from dependence on substances. The individual (or family) exits the cycle of change, and the danger of relapse becomes less acute. In the substance abuse field, some dispute the idea that drug or alcohol problems can be terminated and prefer to think of this stage as remission achieved through maintenance strategies.²²

Conclusion

The fields of substance abuse Counseling and other therapies share many common assumptions, approaches, and techniques, but differ in significant philosophical and practical ways that affect treatment approaches and goals for treatment. Further, within each discipline, theory and practice differ. Although of the two, substance abuse treatment is generally more uniform in its approach, in both cases certain generalizations apply to the practice of the majority of providers. Two concepts essential to both fields are denial and resistance presented by clients.

Even with collaborative efforts, the application of counseling with substance abuse treatment is not as straightforward as it seem. Students and professional must be aware of the issues and challenges involved. In considering evidence-based therapies, Haffman (2007) has cautioned that "we must be vigilant that those programs and services are at least as effective as programs they replace".

Substance abuse counseling is a demanding form of community outreach that requires patience, compassion, and a keen desire to help others who in crisis. A good portion of the addict population is people who need help in many areas of their lives. Often these

people are unaware of the kinds of assistance available, whether they are eligible, or how to go about finding help. Counselors refer patients to a variety of other services that may help provide a stable platform from which they can fight their drug addiction. The abuser may be directed to a family agency, food pantry, physician or psychiatrist, vocational training center, lawyer, welfare agent or other professionals depending on the needs of the individual. One of the most frustrating aspects of the job, counselors report, is the bias that clients typically face when applying for other services. "People hold addicts more responsible for their problems."²³

Substance abuse treatment and family therapy are distinct in their histories, professional organizations, preferred intervention techniques, and focuses of treatment. Counselors in clinical setting or otherwise often face the problem of either "burnout"²⁴ or "dropout" on the behalf of the client. The process though stand by the basic principles of counseling and is supported by the values and ethics of the domain, the notion of individuality and being judgmental about the behavior of the client over shadow the counseling process for clients in substance. An additional skill and knowledge about the clinical and chemical substitute of substance like cocaine and marijuana also helps. It has a direct relation with psychiatric disorders like depression and anxiety.

Notes

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